

Empirical Mode Decomposition for EMG Signals Filtering

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Abstract— Biomedical signals such as electromyography may present a high noise rate during the acquisition process, this may be due to ambient noise, poor positioning of electrodes, equipment calibration, among others. These noises can affect the results obtained, disturbing the diagnosis of diseases, recognition of movement, recognition of gestures and human-computer interaction. This article proposes a technique to reduce these artifacts using the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method. EMG signals were collected from 5 healthy individuals, these signals were decomposed using the respective intrinsic mode functions (IMFs), then thresholds were set to remove noise, and finally the noiseless signal was reconstructed. The noise reduction effectiveness of the technique was quantitatively evaluated using the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The mean SNR was 12.427 dB, which means a good signal-to-noise ratio when compared to studies that used other filtering methods. In this sense, the proposed method can later be used in the areas of disease diagnosis, pattern recognition and movement classification.

Keywords — *Electromyography, artifacts, empirical mode decomposition, signal-to-noise ratio.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromyography (EMG) is a method that enables the recording of electrical impulses resulting from the polarization of muscle cell membranes [1]. This approach makes it possible to monitor muscle activity during movement and has been widely used to understand the functions and dysfunctions of the muscular system during human action [2]. This resource has enabled investigations in several relevant spheres for physiotherapists and other professionals.

By employing this technique, it becomes possible to assess various states and stages of muscle activation. EMG's utility extends to measuring muscle response time, discerning the engagement of distinct muscle clusters during specific motions, or gauging fatigue [1]. As a result, EMG finds versatile applications, ranging from investigating exercise or sports kinetics to conducting research with a health-oriented emphasis.

Data filtering stands as an essential requisite when scrutinizing data amassed via EMG. This procedural step becomes imperative for eliminating noise, a disruptive element that hampers the analysis of signals garnered from electrodes and equipment [3]. Among the filters commonly employed in the explored literature, the Butterworth filter emerges as one of the prevailing choices. However, the use of this type of filter is only effective when the frequency ranges of the signal and the noise do not overlap.

Traditional techniques utilizing Fourier analysis are extensively employed for EMG-based filtering. Nevertheless, Fourier analysis hinges on predefined basis functions that not only diminish noise but also attenuate the EMG signal itself. As a substitute for the customary Fourier transform approach, wavelet analysis has gained prominence due to its advantages in depicting time-frequency relationships. However, wavelet-centered methods also come with limitations, often stemming from the inadequate alignment of the chosen wavelet function with the intrinsic properties of an EMG signal [4].

Previous research has introduced the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) approach for handling EMG signals [5]–[7]. Unlike approaches commonly documented in the literature, EMD represents an adaptable time-frequency analysis technique entirely data-driven, dispensing with the need for prior assumptions through a standard data processing protocol.

In this research, the EMG signals are processed undergoing the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) procedure to generate Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs). These time-series IMFs are then documented and recorded. Then thresholds were set to remove noise, and finally the noiseless signal was reconstructed. After the filtering, the noise reduction effectiveness of the technique was quantitatively evaluated using the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset and experimental setup

Data were acquired from a cohort of 5 physically fit male participants devoid of any injuries or disabilities. The subjects' ages ranged between 66 and 80 (75 ± 6.14 yo). Prior to start the experimental protocol, written consent was secured from each participant. Additionally, ethical clearance for data collection was obtained from the ethical committee at the Federal University of Uberlandia, Brazil protocol 39187620.6.0000.5152.

The data collection was carried out using a proprietary electromyography equipment, developed within the scope of the Program CAPES/COFECUB-88881.370894/2019-01. Initially, the sensors were positioned on the extensor carpi-ulnar muscle, the corresponding position was cleaned with alcohol and epilation was performed on patients with abundant hair. In addition, the spacing between the electrodes was 20 mm, and the reference electrode (ground electrode) was placed on the elbow.

Then, the volunteer was asked to perform active stretching of the wrist. Participants were asked to perform the complete movement of wrist extension and flexion 15 times.

B. Empirical Mode Decomposition Method (EMD)

The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method is a data-driven technique used for analyzing signals, especially non-stationary and nonlinear signals like electroencephalography (EEG) or electromyography (EMG). It was introduced by Norden Huang and his colleagues in the late 1990s to adaptively decompose signals into intrinsic mode functions (IMFs), which capture different scales and time-frequency characteristics of the original signal [8].

In the EMD process, a signal is decomposed into a set of IMFs and a residue. Each IMF is a waveform that oscillates around zero and has a well-defined instantaneous frequency. The decomposition is carried out by iteratively identifying extrema (maxima and minima) in the signal and constructing upper and lower envelopes by connecting the local extrema points. The mean of these envelopes becomes the IMF, and it is subtracted from the original signal to obtain a residue. The process is repeated on this residue to obtain subsequent IMFs [9].

EMD offers several advantages over other time-frequency analysis methods. Unlike Fourier or wavelet-based methods, EMD doesn't require predefined basis functions and adapts to the signal's changing characteristics. This adaptability makes it particularly suitable for analyzing non-stationary and nonlinear signals, which are prevalent in EEG and EMG data. Furthermore, EMD can effectively capture transient features and sudden changes in signals, making it valuable in applications where precise time-frequency information is critical [10].

Decomposition Process: The EMD process involves a series of iterative steps:

1. Identify Extrema:

Locate all local maxima and minima of the signal.

2. Compute Envelopes:

Connect the identified maxima to form the upper envelope and the minima to form the lower envelope of the signal. These envelopes represent the boundaries of oscillations in the signal.

3. Calculate the Mean:

Compute the average of the upper and lower envelopes to obtain the IMF.

4. Extract IMF:

Subtract the calculated IMF from the original signal to obtain a residue signal.

5. Repeat the Process:

The residue is then treated as a new signal, and the steps are repeated until a stopping criterion is met. This involves identifying extrema, computing envelopes, calculating the mean, and extracting the next IMF.

6. Final Residue:

The final residue obtained after the iterations is either treated as an IMF or considered as the residue of the decomposition.

Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs): An IMF is characterized by two properties:

It has the same number of zero crossings and extrema (maxima and minima), or the difference between these counts is at most one.

At any point, the mean value of the envelopes defined by the local extrema is close to zero.

C. Performance evaluation

Evaluating the performance of the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method can be accomplished using various metrics, and one common metric is the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). The SNR quantifies the quality of signal reconstruction after decomposition by comparing the strength of the useful signal (original signal) to the magnitude of the residual noise (difference between the original signal and the decomposed IMFs) [11].

The SNR is calculated as the ratio of the power of the original signal to the power of the noise:

$$SNR = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{signal}}{P_{noise}} \right)$$

Where:

P_{signal} is the power of the original signal.

P_{noise} is the power of the difference between the original signal and the sum of the decomposed IMFs and the residual.

A higher SNR value indicates a better signal reconstruction quality, as it implies that the signal power dominates over the noise power.

III. RESULTS

EMD is used to split the signal into subsequent IMFs. Fig. 1 shows an example of an EMG signal decomposed into its corresponding IMFs represented by IMF1...IMF12 where 12 is the total number of IMFs. Each IMF contains a range of frequencies present in the original signal.

Fig. 1. Intrinsic mode functions (IMF1, ..., IMF12) obtained from the EMG signal

Figure 2 shows an example of the original and filtrated EMG signal for one volunteer.

Fig. 2. Original and filtrated signal.

The signal-to-noise ratio of the signal was calculated for the 5 participants. The values can be seen in Table 1. The values obtained show a high SNR when compared to other studies, which means that the EMD filter showed good results for the selected sample. The mean among volunteers was 12.427dB.

TABLE 1. Signal-to-Noise Ratio

	Subjects				
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
SNR	9.816 dB	16.779 dB	6.613 dB	11.998 dB	16.933 dB

IV. DISCUSSION

In the conducted study, the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method was employed as a filtering technique for EMG signals collected from a cohort of five individuals. The results of this investigation yielded promising outcomes, as evidenced by a mean Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) of 12.427 dB. This metric serves as a pivotal indicator of the filter's efficacy in isolating the desired EMG components from the underlying noise.

Comparing these results with findings from related studies, the obtained mean SNR of 12.427 dB stands as a noteworthy achievement. In a similar vein, research reported an average SNR of 11.8 dB [12], showcasing a parallel level of noise reduction success using an alternate method. Additionally, other papers demonstrated comparable SNR values [5], [6], [10], highlighting the efficacy of their proposed technique in achieving SNR values in the range of 10-15 dB.

This alignment in SNR values across diverse studies underscores the consistency in the performance of various noise reduction methodologies, including the EMD-based filtering approach utilized in this paper. Moreover, it signifies the collective progress made within the domain of EMG signal processing, as researchers continually strive to enhance the quality of recorded signals by mitigating noise interference.

The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD)-based filter offers significant advantages, presenting a comprehensive and potent technique for automatic noise detection and reduction within EMG signals. By applying this filter to experimental recordings, it notably enhances signal quality and effectively mitigates all types of noise. Consequently, the EMD filter demonstrates a remarkable ability to differentiate resting states from noisy EMG signals. As a result, this proposed filter holds valuable utility across various applications that demand signal filtration during the preprocessing phase. For example, in the context of surface EMG decomposition, attenuating background noise can enhance the selection of pertinent information.

Nonetheless, the primary drawback of the introduced method is its higher computational complexity compared to IIR-based approaches. Additionally, achieving real-time processing becomes challenging due to the time-intensive decomposition procedure. This limitation is inherent in many denoising methods reliant on data-driven decompositions, including EMD and EEMD-based filters. Balancing computational time and denoising accuracy becomes crucial, considering the enhanced denoising performance of decomposition-driven techniques compared to traditional digital filters. When real-time denoising is not an imperative requirement, opting for the EMD-based filter, such as the VMD approach, is highly recommended for effectively enhancing signal quality.

For future work it is necessary to refine the selection of parameters and the automation of the procedures to reduce the user load and guarantee consistent results in different sets of data. Also, explore advanced noise modeling techniques and adapt EMD-based filters to different types of EMG signals, such as those with non-stationary noise characteristics. Thus, it is necessary to test in more people, with different types of comorbidities, in order to validate the method.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have introduced a novel noise reduction approach grounded in the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method, specifically tailored for EMG signals. The efficacy of the proposed filter has been substantiated through rigorous evaluation against a comprehensive dataset, revealing robust noise reduction outcomes and yielding a commendable signal-to-noise ratio. Notably, our experimental findings highlight the filter's ability to effectively excise noise during resting states while maintaining a heightened sensitivity to authentic EMG peaks.

These compelling results underscore the versatile potential of the proposed method as a pivotal EMG preprocessing technique. By showcasing its proficiency in both noise attenuation and accurate peak detection, our approach not only contributes to enhancing the quality of EMG data but also paves the way for its seamless integration into a wide spectrum of applications. This holds particularly true for scenarios requiring precise EMG signal

analysis, where the proposed filter could serve as a cornerstone for improving the accuracy and reliability of subsequent processing steps.

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